

////////////////////////////////////

CONNECTING EDUCATION, PRACTICE AND RESEARCH CREATING MEANINGFUL PRODUCTS WITHIN AN INDUSTRIAL DESIGN STUDIO USING A PRODUCT NARRATIVE FRAMEWORK

Rina Bernabei / Kelly Freeman / Jacqueline Power
University of New South Wales / University of New South Wales / University of Tasmania
r.bernabei@unsw.edu.au

ABSTRACT

This paper considers a conceptual design framework that was developed in professional practice. The framework is termed the 'Product Narrative' and is an approach to design that has been developed by the principal authors of this paper in their own award-winning Sydney-based design practice. The Product Narrative framework consists of a four part approach - Narrative; Manufacture; History; and Interaction. This framework offers a means to stimulate a multilayered narrative or story, communicating the ideas of the designers to the end-user via the product. The following paper elaborates on this approach in practice, and describes its implementation in a second year industrial design studio. The perceived value of the Product Narrative is described, and the value of connecting design education with practice.

Keywords: Product Narrative, Design Studio, Pedagogy

INTRODUCTION

Hella Jongerius (2010, p. 187) has noted that "The increasing awareness of the communicative strength of design over the last few decades has led designers to want to give more meaning, more narrative, to their products." This paper explores the value of embedding narratives into products, and the role of the designer in doing so. This is illustrated through a framework called the 'Product Narrative', developed by the authors and implemented in the principal authors own practice. This design framework has been utilized by the principal authors for a university industrial design studio that they coordinate. The primary aim of utilizing this framework in the design studio was to create stronger links to professional

practice through the illustration of a design framework used in practice. It was hoped that the framework would assist students to create 'emotionally sensitive' products, which would in turn shift the studio away from a skills based pursuit, to instead become a sensorial endeavor.

Firstly, the Product Narrative will be described in detail. Secondly, this paper will describe the importance of the industrial design studio and its teaching concerns. Thirdly, the design studio project called *Cultural Dining* based on the Product Narrative will be discussed, including specific examples of student work and qualitative feedback received from the students about the project. Finally, a conclusion will offer final thoughts about the project and a way forward for it in the future.

A CONCEPTUAL DESIGN FRAMEWORK - THE PRODUCT NARRATIVE

Across various disciplines stories or narratives are acknowledged as a powerful way of conveying ideas, yet designers have the added advantage of being able to create physical receptacles for these stories. Designers can intentionally design products that communicate narratives and ideas to end-users, which may create an emotional connection between product and end-user. The resulting products move away from having simple utilitarian value, and become unmistakably associated with their embodied narratives. Hella Jongerius has said that, "Design is never just about use. The function of design lies mainly in its communicative strength, in the story that goes beyond basic functionality... (Jongerius & Schouwenberg, 2010, p. 121). In addition, Professor Kees Dorst (2003, p. 29) explains that:

“when you design you are actually creating two things in parallel: the design itself and the story behind it. This story consists of all the choices that you have made during your design project and the arguments that you used in making them. It is the justification of the design, which explains why the design is constructed the way it is.”

Building on such thinking the authors have developed a framework called the Product Narrative that encompasses a number of ways that a product can communicate with end-users. Essentially the Product Narrative framework offers an approach that can be adopted to stimulate a multilayered narrative or story, communicating the ideas of the designers to the end-user via the product. This is a dynamic process involved with interpreting past or anticipated experiences, stories or narratives (Boje, 1995, p. 997). The Product Narrative framework was developed over many years in the design practice of the principal authors, an award-winning Sydney-based firm called Bernabeifreeman. As the authors are designers as well as academics, this framework has also been the basis of their ongoing design research. The Product Narrative is comprised of four ‘frames’ through which stories might be told or stimulated: Narrative; Manufacture; History; and, Interaction.

- Narrative - told through a two or three-dimensional representation of a story. This method is particularly concerned with the precedence or archetype that the product has referenced.
- Manufacture- this is the story of the craft and craftsman/craftswomen. Traces of the manufacture tell the story of its physical creation.
- History - the personal stories and experiences that the product evokes in the minds of end-users, such as memories of places and people.
- Interaction - a more literal story of the product as a result of interaction with the end-user that may sometimes result in physical changes to it over time.

(Listed adapted from Bernabei & Power, 2010, p. 124).

The authors believe that one of the distinguishing features of the Product Narrative framework is its development by practitioners during ‘action research.’ “Action research is research in which the process of making or designing an artifact constitutes the methodology” (Seago & Dunne, 1999, p. 11). As a result of this approach, practice has directly informed the development of the theory. As the framework developed over time across multiple design projects this allowed it to expand to encompass a range of theoretical approaches. There are some similarities for instance between aspects of the Product Narrative and product semantics, which also sought to provide “a vocabulary and methodology for designing artifacts in view of the meanings they could acquire for their users...” (Krippendorff, 2006, p. 2). Yet other aspects of the Product Narrative, such as the frames of Interaction and Manufacture, have fewer crossovers with the field of product semantics. The breadth of approaches encompassed by the framework is an important feature of it and considered critical to its success and relevance. Importantly however, the framework remains concise by treating broad areas under ‘frames.’ The four frames can be applied individually, or simultaneously. As a result, the manageability of the framework makes it suitable to be applied by designers in professional practice and also used by educators in the design studio. The nomenclature of the frames allows approaches to be easily described and discussed during the design process.

The application of the Product Narrative is evident in Bernabeifreeman products (Figure 1). The *Seams Light* conveys a theme common to many of the Bernabeifreeman products, that of traditional feminine textile practices and the decorative place textiles once held within the home. Bernabeifreeman have been described as “pioneers of a design approach that reconciles two seeming opposites: brute masculinity of industrial manufacture and the soft, tactile, decorative quality of traditional textile crafts” (Howes, 2006, p. 58). In the *Seams Light* the frame of Narrative has been focused upon. For the

form of the *Seams Light* Bernabeifreeman (2011) “was inspired by traditional archetypal cloth lampshades. Bernabeifreeman reinterpreted the language of pleating, gathering, and stretching fabric over frames to produce three diverse pendant lamps.”

Figure 1. Bernabeifreeman ‘Seams Light.’

The frame of Interaction forms a focus in the Bernabeifreeman *Lace Light* (Figure 2). Interaction between a product and end-user may result in new stories forming as the product physically changes overtime. Yet interaction may sometimes be subtler. In the case of the *Lace Light* a level of interaction occurs each time the light is switched on by the end-user and a delicate network of shadows is cast across the room creating instant yet temporary decoration (Bernabei, Freeman & Power, 2008). These shadows allude to wallpaper, once a popular feature of the domestic interior.

Not only is the Product Narrative evident in the work of Bernabeifreeman, research by the authors has uncovered that similarly it can also be found in the work of other contemporary product designers such as Hella Jongerius and Tokujin Yoskioka (Bernabei, Freeman & Power, 2011). Thus the telling of stories through products is an approach adopted by a number of designers, but achieved in various ways. The broad and descriptive nature of the Product Narrative frames enables them to be used to analyze a variety of contemporary products, which is considered by the authors to be an important feature of the framework. Contemporary products by

international designers are often experienced non-directly through images and qualitative descriptions rather than through direct experience of the product. Thus the Product Narrative provides a communication tool between designers enabling them to explain their design approaches, as well as analyze the approaches of others.

Figure 2. Bernabeifreeman ‘Lace Light.’

The Product Narrative is also deemed valuable as it provides a greater opportunity for the end-user to develop a connection with the product, deem it of value, and thereby have it remain in their possession. In this way no matter its monetary value, the product might be considered ‘valuable’ because of its associated stories. As Hella Jongerius (2010, p. 302) has said, “Both the recent economic crisis and the threat of climate change have made the question of legitimation topical and necessary again. How many things do we need to own?” Perhaps the products already owned might quell the consumer thirst for acquiring ‘more things’, if end-users consider what they already possess as valuable. The retention of products by end-users as a result of them being legitimized because of the stories associated with them, therefore has broad implications beyond the keeping of the immediate product.

THE INDUSTRIAL DESIGN STUDIO

The design studio has traditionally provided the forum in which to train budding designers. The importance of the design studio has lead to it being described as “the champion subject for teaching

designers” (Clune, 2010, p. 86). The primary aim of the design studio is “to equip the student as a professional. Hence studio work frequently relies on a reconstruction or simulation of the circumstances of practice” (Özturk & Turkkan, 2006, p. 97).

The challenge for design educators is to orchestrate exciting and inspiring design studio projects for students. Within the safety of the design studio, students develop their practical skills yet the design briefs must also wield the potential to elevate the design thinking of students. If the brief incorporates examples from practice and real life methodologies, hopefully it will stretch students beyond foundational level design skills to the next level of design thinking. As designers, researchers and educators, it was these thoughts that led us to develop an industrial design studio project called *Cultural Dining* based on the Product Narrative framework. It has always been the aims of the principal authors to bring their research of the Product Narrative framework into the design studio, to inform both the learning outcomes of the studio, as well as the research itself.

The implementation of the Product Narrative framework in the studio was also a response to a perceived lack of scaffolding provided to students in the development of their designs. While the design brief traditionally mimics how the design process may unfold in practice, including the final assessment of the outcome by a ‘client’ modeled in the form of a design jury, specific approaches adapted from industry to inform the design in its development phases often seems to be lacking. As articulated by Stephen J. Clune (2010, p. 86) “The studio has a heavy orientation on ‘how to design’, but the question of ‘what to design’ is not always afforded to the student.” The ‘how to design’ is interpreted by the authors as taking the form of correct drawing and model-making techniques, whilst ‘what to design’ or the conceptual framework to underpin the design approach, rarely seems to be a major focus of pedagogic techniques employed by design educators. It seems self-evident that students should be provided with a clear framework and appropriate terminology within which to work as designers, however in the experience of the authors,

this is often not provided and therefore misses an important opportunity in which the students might engage in ‘deep’ learning about design.

The design studio is generally considered to facilitate ‘deep’ learning approaches. Two commonly used terms in education that “describe ways of learning a particular task” are ‘deep’ and ‘surface’ learning (Biggs & Tang, 1999, p. 20). ‘Deep’ learning occurs when students feel the task is meaningful and consequently endeavour to learn underlying principles and the detail that support concepts (Biggs & Tang, 1999, p. 24). The so-called ‘surface’ approach to learning occurs when students work to complete a task, simply to satisfy what is required to progress through the course at a basic level. It has been suggested by Stephen J. Clune (2010) that industrial design generally satisfies ‘deep’ learning approaches, particularly as a result of the importance placed on the design studio. Clune (2010) says:

“Industrial Design would appear to be in an advanced position with regards to deep learning, as the constructivist approach of ‘learning by doing’ is a staple in design courses: Industrial Design almost teaches Deep Learning by default.” (p. 88).

It is recognized that experimentation through design as often occurs in the design studio, a technique that has its roots in “the classical Schools (Bauhaus, etc.)”, provides an important learning opportunity (Boucharenc, 2006, p. 6). By teaching the students to approach design through a framework, the authors do not wish to promote a ‘surface’ approach to learning. On the contrary, it is proposed that providing students with a framework to approach design may in fact foster so called ‘deep learning.’ The authors believe that by providing a design methodology or framework, they are giving the students a guideline for the design thinking process, rather than a prescriptive format for developing a product. The framework describes the process of achieving a ‘type’ of design, the expertise required and the roles played by the designer. In a sense, it outlines a series of design thinking tasks that the student must engage in. For many students, particularly those that have difficulty approaching a

design problem, the framework is of most benefit; it helps improve confidence and understanding of design by providing a way forward.

The Product Narrative framework, which the authors drew upon from their own practice, also creates a link between industry and the design studio through methodology/theory. The role of industry in the design studio has been much discussed, particularly in reference to collaborative professional practice or 'real life' projects. In this paper, we want to also emphasize the importance of having a practicing designer/educator within the design studio, and the benefit of this to the students. Van den Akker (1999, p. 8) points out that, "In the search for innovative 'solutions' for educational problems, interaction with practitioners is essential." It is both the industry experiences and personal design methodologies of the practitioner that are of value to the students. Interaction with practitioners gives students the opportunity to see beyond the design studio and understand how the skills they are being taught extend beyond into professional practice.

In this case of the Product Narrative being implemented in the design studio, it is important to highlight that all the lecturers and tutors were familiar with the Product Narrative, as a result of practice with the principal authors. Not only were the lecturers/tutors engaged with the Product Narrative but they were also experienced educators and understood the parameters of the project from an educational perspective. The industrial design course at the University of New South Wales has a long history of using practitioners as educators in the design studio, and in fact it relies on them to help inform students about current manufacturing, costing and design process methods used in industry.

The importance of having practice-based educators teaching in the design studio is highlighted by the *Australian Learning and Teaching Council* (2011) in its *Strategies For Effective Practice within Studio Teaching* which states that "Staff quality (academic and technical) is integral to the success of studios. Elements of staff quality include: an appropriate balance of professional experience and teaching experience; an ability to integrate professional

practice and studio teaching; the ability of staff to cooperate effectively in the teaching process with colleagues; and an ability to successfully facilitate student learning through studio projects (and intervene where necessary)."

Many practice-based educators share this view. Ruth McDermott (pers. comm., May 2011), who is a respected Sydney-based designer with extensive studio teaching experience believes that industry experience is of great benefit as "Design projects seldom go to plan - there are always ups and downs, wrong turns, disasters etc.,. Practitioners are experienced in slogging through and getting the project up. Agile thinking and adaptability are necessary -we understand that theory is good but applying it can be challenging."

Similarly, Berto Pandolfo who heads the Industrial Design program at the University of Technology, Sydney, thinks it is important to use practicing designers from industry to assist with the complexity and the demanding nature of advanced studios. According to Pandolfo, practitioners are "able to bring to their teaching a relevance and expertise that enable them to be able to teach advanced and challenging studios" (pers. comm., May 2011).

Whilst practicing designers have long provided students with technical information and the latest digital design skills, they are not often used to providing theoretical underpinning to design thinking. To help achieve 'deep' learning within the design studio, it is our belief that utilization of practice based methods and theory can only deepen the understanding of the whole design process for students.

The merits of connecting practice and studio teaching are important not only for the student but for the design educator/practitioner. After developing the Product Narrative framework over many years in practice, and collecting feedback and critique, the ability to use it in a design studio context further clarifies its value and broadens its application. The practitioner is able to apply the framework and support it with advanced market exposure, current research trends, as well as

industry experience in manufacturing processes, market evaluation and cost analysis. The student however uses it as more of a ‘blue sky’ idea platform to enrich and feed the creative process. Having had the opportunity to test the framework in a design studio context, it was possible to see new possibilities for its use. As the Product Narrative is broad and does encompass many different approaches, it was found that it was very useful in group discussions and brainstorming early on in the design process, as a way of generating abstract ideas for potential design concepts. The authors also felt that the broad, yet specific nature of the framework would also be beneficial to other fields of design that dealt with production, such as graphic design, fashion/textile design and interior design.

THE DESIGN STUDIO PROJECT

The design studio project *Cultural Dining* was carried out with second year industrial design students in the second semester of the teaching calendar at the University of New South Wales. Students were considered far enough advanced in their design education to be able to utilize this design framework. While exposing students to methods used in practice in the first year of their design education may be beneficial, it is our belief that until fundamental skills such as sketching, modeling and drawing are developed, students are not fully equipped to apply the methods.

Variations of the *Cultural Dining* project have been developed over the past five years by the principal authors. In 2009 and 2010, the outlined Product Narrative framework was applied to the *Cultural Dining* project. The design brief reflects a broader trend in the Industrial Design program, that has seen a restructuring to introduce a greater degree of design theory to the course as a complement to the technical skills developed by the students.

The *Cultural Dining* project commenced with the introduction of the brief, with the four weeks thereafter being dedicated to design development. The project culminated with the final design being assessed by a formal design jury. The cohort of sixty or so students was broken down into tutorial groups of approximately twenty students led by a

lecturer/tutor who were each familiar with the concept of the Product Narrative.

Prior to commencing design development, students were required to research the role of dining in their selected culture and produce an essay. In addition, students produced a mood board providing a visual illustration of what they had uncovered in the course of their research. The authors believe that the focus of the brief on *Cultural Dining* provided a rich source of precedence, ranging from emotion to cultural history that was suitable for the Product Narrative framework. The project offered the memories of food ritual, alongside contemporary food identity, technology and culture.

After the introduction of the design brief, students were presented with a lecture outlining ‘what’ and ‘how’ Product Narratives are used by designers. Examples of work were shown of several well known designers, including the work produced by the lecturers in their own practice. The framework was explained in detail and students were instructed how to use it. Over the following three weeks, students worked with tutors/lecturers using the framework throughout the design process, from concept generation, to manufacturing detail. The framework was not used in a prescriptive way; rather it became part of the overall design brief. Whenever a student was at a standstill or couldn’t decide how to proceed, the instructors questioned the design in terms of one or more of the principles of the framework. It helped students evaluate what aspects of the food ritual or food culture they wanted to vocalize through the physical design.

Figure 3. Student Julian's 'Hong Kong Milk tea.'

An example can be seen in the work by student Julian, who wished to reintroduce the ceremony and gestures of Hong Kong Milk tea or *dai pai dong* milk tea (Figure 3). Julian wanted to explore Interaction through his product focusing on the 'pulling of the milk.' This intention resulted in him designing a handle which is required to be pulled before pouring, thereby narrating the story of the skill and ceremony of the tea maker. He also explored visual narrative, with the final form echoing the traditional aluminum jugs used in Hong Kong. In addition, the motif on the red anodized exterior speaks of its Chinese cultural heritage.

When asked if this project helped him understand "what to design" or "how to design" Julian answered:

"Design for Dining was indeed a project I really enjoyed, it was a project I can really express my own cultural background and allowed me to bring together the rituals of traditional Hong Kong milk tea in combination with modern technology into designing a product that enlightens Hong Kong tea culture. As an Australian born Chinese, this project has also given me the opportunity to apply my background in Chinese art and calligraphy, as well as teaching me how the clash of east meets west can influence the birth of a new product."

Julian also pointed out the importance of having an insight to a practice-based lecturers' research saying:

"I believe lecturers who do this opens up pathways to discovery, it allows us to take in their points of success and utilise them to our own practice."

Another student Daniele comments:

"The Dining and Design brief showed us a method of how to design certain products. It was beneficial as it demonstrated the iteration process and how it could benefit the design process and final product as we could produce a design which was much richer in interaction and connections made with the user."

Figure 4. Student Fiona's 'Rebirth' teacups.

For Fiona a Chinese student who explored the ancient ritual of tea drinking, the Product Narrative framework gave her a method to approach both Interaction and Manufacture in an innovative way. Her teacup design was made up of a very thin outer shell of porcelain over a partly silicon inner core (Figure 4). The cup was also printed with thermochromic ink. The end-user cracked the cup when it was taken in their hand. This individualized the artifact and also referenced ancient teacups, which often had cracks, repaired with gold. These gold cracks became a feature of the traditional cup. When the cup designed by Fiona was filled with hot tea, a traditional oriental pattern in thermochromic ink emerged on the cup, again linking it to its history and use. The history of the tea tradition as well as the artifact was explored through the Product Narrative framework.

Fiona found the Product Narrative:

"important for new design students because it gives them a starting point and a direction to go with. However I find that it is much more important for current design students because they can gather more knowledge of different ways to approach design and it can also be just an interesting story that they will remember and discuss with each other."

Although not all projects were as successful as those illustrated, many students commented that the framework gave them a way 'into' the project. One student for instance said:

“It’s shown me the “light” in the hows, whys and whos of a product. It’s actually made me further question, why certain products have to be designed that certain way or is there another idea to design it.”

Although several students commented that the framework helped enrich their understanding of the project, it is questionable whether the project would have achieved the same outcomes had not all of the lecturers and tutors had practice experience and in particular, familiarity with the Product Narrative framework. The enhanced experience alone of practitioner participation in the studio, gave this project a ‘deeper’ level of interaction.

A WAY FORWARD

How might this studio brief and framework be implemented in future design studios taking onboard what has been learned? And what are the merits of connecting practice and design studio teaching in this way?

In the future, when using this studio brief individual tutorial groups may each be given a different frame of the Product Narrative to explore. This has both positive and negative aspects that need to be considered by the lecturers/tutors. A positive outcome may be that students will develop a rigorous approach to one of these frames and understand it in detail. A negative feature is that it may be too confining and of course, not all students may be suited to a particular approach. In addition, generally more than one of these frames is implemented in a product to enable a multilayered story to be communicated, as illustrated in the examples of student work described. Careful consideration must be made of these issues in any future use of this project.

In any future implementation of the project, the authors have considered that documentation by the students of their process in visual diaries may be beneficial in further improving the project. The visual diaries of students may aid in providing further insights into how the project may be improved in meeting the needs of students and their individual learning styles.

CONCLUSIONS

Clearly, the value of connecting research, practice and design studio teaching presents a cornucopia of opportunities for practitioners and students alike. As articulated by Ruth McDermott, “Students like working with people who have practice experience, they want to feel connected with industry and the profession. They like the stories of projects, the disasters avoided, supplier relationships, and funny stories about clients” (pers. comm., May 2011). The Product Narrative framework and its implementation in the *Cultural Dining* project is just one example of how practitioners may be able to communicate their design framework to students, it is hoped in the future there might be many more examples. Of course, this synthesis is not always achievable or possible because practice and design research does not always cross over with the learning outcomes of the design studio. In a traditional design studio model, it is understood that the master-apprentice relationship when at its best, involves a dynamic two-way path that allows learning on all sides. Perhaps the most important aspect of connecting practice, research and studio teaching for a university design course is the building of a strong culture of design.

REFERENCES

- Australian Learning and Teaching Council, *Studio Teaching Project*, viewed 16 May 2011, <www.studioteaching.org>.
- Bernabeifreeman. (2011) *Tactile Imaginations*, viewed 30 August 2011, <<http://www.bernabeifreeman.com.au>>.
- Bernabei, R., Freeman, K., Power, J. (2011) Chapter 24: The Value of Storytelling in Product Design. In: A. Silva & R. Simoes (Ed.), *Handbook of Research on Trends in Product Design and Development: technological and organizational perspectives*. Hershey, New York: IGI Global, 447-460.
- Bernabei, R., Power, J. (2010) Using a Narrative Framework in an Industrial Design Studio to Create Meaningful Products. In: G. Forsyth (Ed.), *Connected 2010: 2nd International Conference on Design Education*, 28 June - 1 July, Sydney, Australia, 123-127.
- Bernabei, R., Freeman, K., Power, J. (2008) Designers as Storytellers: the weaving of narratives in the work of Bernabeifreeman. In: P. M. A. Desmet (et. al) (Ed.) *Proceedings from the 6th Conference on Design and Emotion 2008*, October 6-9, Hong Kong SAR.
- Biggs J., Tang C. (2007) *Teaching for Quality Learning at University: what the student does*. 3rd edition, Berkshire: Open University Press.
- Boje, D.M. (1995) Stories of the Storytelling Organization: a postmodern analysis of Disney as ‘Tamara-Land’. *The Academy of Management Journal*, Vol. 28, 997.

- Boucharenc, C. G. (2006) Research on Basic Design Education: an international survey. *International Journal of Technology and Design Education*, Vol. 16, No. 1, 1-30.
- Clune, S. J. (2010) Deep Learning and Industrial Design Education for Sustainability. In: G. Forsyth (Ed.), *Connected 2010: 2nd International Conference on Design Education*, 28 June - 1 July, Sydney, Australia, 86-90.
- Dorst, K (2003) *Understanding Design: 150 reflections on being a designer*. Amsterdam: BIS Publishers.
- Howes, E. 2006 Chapter BF Bernabeifreman. In B. Parkes (Ed.), *Freestyle New Australian Design for Living*. Sydney: Object: Australian Centre for Craft and Design.
- Jongerius, H., Schouwenberg, L. (2010) *Hella Jongerius: misfit*. London: Phaidon Press.
- Krippendorff, K. (2006) *The Semantic Turn: a new foundation for design*. London: CRC Press.
- Öztürk, M.N., Turkkkan, E.E. (2006) The Design Studio as Teaching/Learning Medium - a process-based approach. *Journal of Art and Design Education*, Vol. 21, No. 1, 96-104.
- Seago, A., Dunne, A. (1999) New Methodologies in Art and Design Research: the object as discourse. *Design Issues*, Vol. 15, No. 2, 11-17.
- van den Akker, J., Frick, T.H.W, Reiguth, C.M. (1999) *Design Approaches and Tools in Education Training*. Netherlands, Kluwer Publisher.